

UTILIZATION OF GAME-BASED ASSESSMENT IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES: BASIS FOR TEACHER'S IMPLEMENTATION GUIDE

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the utilization of game-based assessment (GBA) in Physical Education classes as the basis for developing a Teacher's Implementation Guide. Using a descriptive quantitative research design, the researchers surveyed 112 Senior High School students from the College of Sciences, Technology and Communications (CSTC) in selected schools in Sariaya, Quezon. A researcher-made questionnaire was employed to gather data, which were analyzed using weighted mean as the statistical treatment. The study explored how GBA influences key areas such as student engagement, learner motivation, and academic achievement in PE. Findings revealed that students strongly agreed GBA strategies made PE classes more engaging, enjoyable, and meaningful. Activities such as the Relay Race Challenge, Fitness Bingo, Throwing Accuracy Challenge, and Sport Skill Relay were identified as effective tools in increasing student interest, participation, and comprehension of physical education concepts. Based on the results, the researchers developed a Teacher's Implementation Guide that contains structured, curriculum-based GBA activities with step-by-step procedures and assessment rubrics aligned with the K to 12 curriculum. This guide aims to assist teachers in applying GBA methods effectively in their classrooms. The study concluded that game-based assessment is a highly effective and innovative approach to improving instructional delivery and learner outcomes in PE, making it a valuable addition to pedagogical practices.

Keywords: *Game-Based Assessment, Physical Education, Student Engagement, Learner Motivation, Teacher's Implementation Guide, Performance Tasks*

INTRODUCTION

Game-Based Assessment (GBA) is an innovative approach that integrates assessment tools within interactive and engaging gameplay. It allows learners to demonstrate their skills, knowledge, and competencies in a dynamic learning environment while collecting real-time data on their performance (Lin et al., 2020). Unlike traditional assessments, GBA provides a more immersive and adaptive evaluation process, reducing test anxiety and improving the measurement of both cognitive and non-cognitive skills Wang et al.(2022). It incorporates gamified elements such as challenges, rewards, and interactive feedback, fostering a deeper connection between learning and assessment Chen et al.(2020).

Moreover, the use of GBA in education offers several benefits. It increases learner engagement and motivation by transforming assessments into enjoyable activities (El Mawas et al., 2022). Research has shown that GBA can improve academic performance and foster active participation, particularly in subjects requiring hands-on application, such as Physical Education (Acquah & Katz, 2020; Xie et al., 2021). In addition, it provides instant feedback, helping students recognize and correct errors in real time thereby supporting continuous learning (Wang et al., 2022).

However, implementing GBA is not without challenges. Designing effective game-based assessments require technological resources and pedagogical expertise, which may not be readily available in all educational settings (Kim & Ifenthaler, 2019). Furthermore, ensuring the validity and reliability of results can be complex, as different game mechanics may influence learners' performance in diverse ways (Landers & Sanchez, 2022). Despite these limitations, many educators continue to explore GBA as a promising alternative to conventional evaluation methods.

In the context of Physical Education (PE), GBA aligns well with the subject's active and experiential nature. PE classes offer a range of physical activities, including sports, dance, and fitness routines that support students' physical, cognitive, and social development (Cheung et al., 2018). Traditionally, assessment in PE includes both written and practical tasks. However, conventional methods often fail to capture the full scope of student abilities, especially in performance-based activities. As such, game-based assessments are becoming a preferred strategy for making evaluations more interactive, motivating, and reflective of actual student learning (Bui et al., 2023; Harvey & Marlatt, 2021).

In the Philippine educational setting, the Department of Education supports more meaningful and performance-based evaluation methods. DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015, titled Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program, emphasizes the need for varied, authentic, and real-life aligned assessments, particularly in performance-heavy subjects like PE. Similarly, DepEd Order No. 31, s.

2020, Interim Guidelines for Assessment and Grading in Light of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan, promotes alternative strategies such as performance tasks to ensure active learner engagement. In alignment with these policies, GBA presents itself as a practical and effective tool for enhancing motivation, capturing holistic student progress, and improving assessment in Physical Education.

From the premise mentioned above, the researchers aimed to determine the perceived effects of using game-based assessment tools in PE classes in senior high school.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the perceived effects of utilization of Game-based Assessment in Physical Education classes as basis for Teacher's Implementation Guide. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the game-based assessment tools utilized in their classes for:
 - 1.1 written works; and
 - 1.2 performance task?
2. What are the perceived effects of the game-based assessment tools on the students in terms of:
 - 2.1 Engagement
 - 2.2 Motivation; and
 - 2.3 Learner's Achievements?
3. What Teacher's Implementation guide can be suggested based on the research findings?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive research design in a quantitative approach to determine the perceived effects on the utilization of a game-based assessment tool in physical education classes as a basis for a teacher's implementation guide.

According to Barella et al. (2024), quantitative research involves the use of numerical data and statistical analysis to obtain, analyze, and explain information. This design was appropriate for the study because it allowed the researchers to systematically measure and determine the perceived effects of game-based assessment tools on students' learning achievement, motivation, and engagement in physical education.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in one private institution in Sariaya, Quezon that offers Senior High School Program. The institution provided an ideal setting for the study due to its diverse student body and the integration of game-based assessment tools in its Physical Education curriculum.

One of the key reasons for selecting this school was its diverse population. With learners coming from various backgrounds, the researchers saw an opportunity to gather well-rounded insights into how game-based assessments can work across different types of students. The school was also open and supportive of the study, which made the research process more collaborative and meaningful.

By conducting the study in this locale, the researchers aimed to understand how game-based assessments are being applied in practice and, more importantly, how they can be improved. The goal was to create an implementation guide that is not only research-based but also grounded in the actual experiences of both teachers and students within a real educational environment.

Respondents and Sampling Technique

The respondents of this study were Senior High School students from one private institution in Sariaya, Quezon, who were enrolled during the academic year 2024 –2025. The total student population of the chosen locale consisted of 713 students. For this study, the researchers specifically focused on Grade 12 students, as they were expected to provide valuable insights into their experiences.

To ensure a diverse representation of perspectives, the researchers used a purposive sampling technique to select the respondents. As emphasized by Campbell et al. (2020), purposive sampling allows for a better match between the sample and the aims and objectives of the research, thereby increasing the quality of the study and the reliability of the data and conclusions.

The respondents were selected using a purposive sampling technique with the following criteria: enrolled as a Grade 12 student in the chosen locale, had already utilized a game-based assessment tool during PE classes, and were available and willing to participate in the study. A total of one hundred twelve (112) Grade 12 students were selected as respondents for this study.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers undertook several steps to gather the necessary data for the study. After the questionnaire was examined and validated, the researchers formally sought permission from the school principal to conduct the data collection. The purpose and scope of the study were clearly explained, and the researchers assured the principal that all collected data would be used solely for academic purposes and would remain confidential.

Upon receiving approval, the researchers coordinated with the teachers in charge of the Grade 12 Senior High School students who met the established criteria for participation. The teachers assisted in distributing the online survey via Google Forms to their students.

Before students accessed the survey, the researchers provided the teachers with information about the study's purpose, the voluntary nature of participation, and the confidentiality and anonymity of responses. The teachers then relayed this information to the students. Informed consent was obtained electronically through the Google Form, and students were informed that participation was voluntary and that they could withdraw at any time without penalty. These ethical considerations were strictly observed to protect the rights and welfare of the participants throughout the data gathering process.

Research Instrument

The researchers utilized a self-made survey checklist questionnaire to determine the perceived effects of the utilization of game-based assessment tools in physical education classes. The questionnaire consisted of two parts.

The first part identifies the game-based assessment tools commonly used in physical education classes, particularly in written works and performance tasks. The second part focuses on the perceived effects of these assessment tools on student engagement, motivation, and learning achievements.

The first part contains twelve options while the second part contains thirty statements, resulting in a total of forty-two. For the second part, the researchers employed a 4-Point Likert Scale, where 4 represents Strongly Agree (SA), 3 represents Agree (A), 2 represents Disagree (D), and 1 represents Strongly Disagree (SD).

Statistical Treatment of Data

To accurately interpret the data, the following statistical treatments were utilized:

For Research Question 1, Frequency and Percentage Distribution was used to determine the most commonly utilized game-based assessment tools in Physical Education classes. The formula was shown below as:

$$\% = \frac{f}{N} \times 100$$

Where:

% = percentage

f = frequency or number of cases in any categories

N = total number of cases in all categories

For Research Question 2, Weighted Arithmetic Mean was used to determine the perceived effects of the utilization of game-based assessment tools on learner engagement, motivation, and achievements. The formula was shown below as:

$$W = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i X_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i}$$

Where:

W = Weighted Mean

n = number of terms to be averaged

W_i = weights applied to x values

X_i = data values to be averaged

The researchers used a 4-point Likert Scale and interpret the result using the continuous scale below

Point Scale	Mean Range	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.26 - 4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.51 - 3.25	Agree
2	1.76 - 2.50	Disagree
1	1.00 - 1.75	Strongly Disagree

Scope and Limitations

This study aimed to determine the perceived effects of using game-based assessment tools in physical education classes as a basis for crafting a Teacher's Implementation Guide. The respondents in this study were Grade 12 students from one of the private secondary schools in Sariaya, Quezon, which offered Senior High School programs. The respondents were selected using the purposive sampling technique with the following criteria: enrolled as a Grade 12 student in the chosen locale, had already utilized a game-based assessment tool during PE classes, and were available and willing to participate in the study. This study is descriptive and quantitative in nature. The researchers utilized a self-made survey checklist questionnaire to gather the needed information. To analyze it, the researchers used frequency distribution and weighted arithmetic mean. The study was completed within one month, allowing for focused data collection and thorough analysis.

Nevertheless, the researchers faced several limitations, particularly during the data gathering phase. One major problem was the limited timeframe, as data gathering occurred with the end of the academic year. With the onset of the school vacation, there was insufficient time to personally distribute and retrieve responses from all targeted respondents. To overcome this, the researchers crafted a self-designed questionnaire into a Google Form and disseminated it online with the help of one of the PE teachers of the target respondents. This allowed students to respond at their convenience, even beyond school hours. Although this method helped improve the response rate within the tight schedule, it also depended largely on students having internet access and being self-motivated to participate. Despite these constraints, the researchers successfully collected enough data for analysis by adapting their methods and making effective use of digital resources.

RESULTS

The following sections discuss the implementation of game-based assessment (GBA) tools in Physical Education (PE), focusing on their usage in written works and performance tasks, and how these tools affect students' engagement, motivation, and academic achievement. References from related literature are also used to strengthen the findings and provide a solid theoretical grounding.

Part I. Game-Based Assessment Tools

Table 1. Game-Based Assessment Tools Utilized in Physical Education Classes in terms of Written Works

Game-Based Assessment Tool	Frequency	Percent
Capture the Flag Strategy	12	10.7
Capture the Flag Strategy, Simon Says Strategy, Sport Skill Relay Strategy	1	.9
Capture the Flag Strategy, Sport Skill Relay Strategy	1	.9
Catch and Throw Games	20	17.9
Catch and Throw Games, Capture the Flag Strategy	1	.9
Catch and Throw Games, Capture the Flag Strategy, Sport Skill Relay Strategy, Fitness Tic-Tac-Toe Strategy	1	.9
Catch and Throw Games, Fitness Bingo Strategy	1	.9
Catch and Throw Games, Fitness Bingo Strategy, Capture the Flag Strategy, Simon Says Strategy, Sport Skill Relay Strategy, Fitness Tic-Tac-Toe Strategy	3	2.7
Catch and Throw Games, Fitness Bingo Strategy, Sport Skill Relay Strategy, Fitness Tic-Tac-Toe Strategy	1	.9
Catch and Throw Games, Simon Says Strategy, Sport Skill Relay Strategy	1	.9
Catch and Throw Games, Sport Skill Relay Strategy	2	1.8
Fitness Bingo Strategy	14	12.5
Fitness Bingo Strategy, Capture the Flag Strategy, Fitness Tic-Tac-Toe Strategy	1	.9
Fitness Bingo Strategy, Fitness Tic-Tac-Toe Strategy	1	.9
Fitness Bingo Strategy, Sport Skill Relay Strategy, Fitness Tic-Tac-Toe Strategy	1	.9
Fitness Tic-Tac-Toe Strategy	15	13.4
Simon Says Strategy	8	7.1
Sport Skill Relay Strategy	28	25.0
Total	112	100.0

Table 2. Game-Based Assessment Tools Utilized in Physical Education Classes in terms of Performance Task

Game-Based Assessment Tool	Frequency	Percent
Catching and Dodging	10	8.9
Cooperative Ball Pass	16	14.3
Fitness Circuit	16	14.3
Fitness Circuit, Target Shooting Challenge, Cooperative Ball Pass	1	.9
Relay Race Challenge	30	26.8
Relay Race Challenge, Catching and Dodging, Fitness Circuit	1	.9
Relay Race Challenge, Catching and Dodging, Target Shooting Challenge, Cooperative Ball Pass	1	.9
Relay Race Challenge, Fitness Circuit	1	.9
Relay Race Challenge, Fitness Circuit, Cooperative Ball Pass	1	.9
Relay Race Challenge, Fitness Circuit, Target Shooting Challenge, Cooperative Ball Pass	1	.9
Relay Race Challenge, Throwing Accuracy Challenge	2	1.8
Relay Race Challenge, Throwing Accuracy Challenge, Catching and Dodging, Fitness Circuit, Target Shooting Challenge	1	.9
Relay Race Challenge, Throwing Accuracy Challenge, Catching and Dodging, Fitness Circuit, Target Shooting Challenge, Cooperative Ball Pass	4	3.6
Relay Race Challenge, Throwing Accuracy Challenge, Fitness Circuit	1	.9
Relay Race Challenge, Throwing Accuracy Challenge, Fitness Circuit, Target Shooting Challenge, Cooperative Ball Pass	1	.9
Target Shooting Challenge	6	5.4
Target Shooting Challenge, Cooperative Ball Pass	1	.9
Throwing Accuracy Challenge	17	15.2
Throwing Accuracy Challenge, Catching and Dodging, Cooperative Ball Pass	1	.9
Total	112	100.0

Part II. Perceived Effects of the Utilization of Game-based Assessment Tools

Table 3. Perceived Effects of the Utilization of Game-Based Assessment Tools in terms of Engagement

No	Statement	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
3	Helps me to be more actively involved during PE class.	3.64	Strongly Agree
6	Makes it highly engaging due to its compelling content, clear structure, and ability to sustain my interest.	3.54	Strongly Agree
7	Makes me want to participate more in PE class.	3.53	Strongly Agree
5	Motivates me to continue completing tasks in PE class.	3.51	Strongly Agree
1	Makes the PE classes more enjoyable than the use of traditional assessment.	3.49	Strongly Agree
4	Allows me to see the positive impact in my learning experience.	3.49	Strongly Agree
8	Captures my attention effectively.	3.49	Strongly Agree
9	Makes me feel like I am playing while learning.	3.48	Strongly Agree
2	Keeps me focused during PE Class	3.46	Strongly Agree
10	Makes me feel like I belong to the class	3.51	Strongly Agree
Weighted Average Mean		3.51	Strongly Agree

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean and VI for verbal interpretation was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Strongly Disagree (SD), the range of 1.76 - 2.50 indicates Disagree (D), the range of 2.51 - 3.25 indicates Agree (A), and 3.26 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree (SA).

Table 4. Perceived Effects of the Utilization of Game-Based Assessment Tools in terms of Motivation

No	Statement	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
9	Enhances my confidence with my own abilities.	3.57	Strongly Agree
8	Increases my level of confidence towards PE.	3.52	Strongly Agree
10	Inspires me to believe that my goals are attainable.	3.50	Strongly Agree
2	Makes me more excited to learn.	3.48	Strongly Agree
3	Motivates me to push my limits and perform better.	3.48	Strongly Agree
5	Encourages teamwork and collaboration.	3.46	Strongly Agree
1	Motivates me to improve my performance.	3.45	Strongly Agree
4	Makes me want to learn more about the subject matter.	3.45	Strongly Agree
6	Motivates me to achieve higher scores when they are used.	3.45	Strongly Agree
7	Makes me want to practice my skills outside of class.	3.42	Strongly Agree
Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.48	Strongly Agree

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean and VI for verbal interpretation was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Strongly Disagree (SD), the range of 1.76 - 2.50 indicates Disagree (D), the range of 2.51 - 3.25 indicates Agree (A), and 3.26 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree (SA).

Table 5. Perceived Effects of the Utilization of Game-Based Assessment Tools in terms of Learners Achievements

No	Statement	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
8	Gives me the chance to show what I know and what I can do in PE.	3.46	Strongly Agree
4	Helps me perform better in PE.	3.45	Strongly Agree
10	Teaches me to learn valuable life skills.	3.45	Strongly Agree
9	Helps me understand the purpose of physical activities.	3.44	Strongly Agree
3	Helps me remember what I've learned because of the strategies of the games.	3.43	Strongly Agree
1	Helps me to understand the lessons easily.	3.41	Strongly Agree
2	Provides me new skills I can use in my class.	3.41	Strongly Agree
6	Helps me apply what I've learned in PE to real life situations.	3.41	Strongly Agree
7	Makes me feel that I'm improving my physical skills.	3.38	Strongly Agree
5	Helps me track my progress.	3.30	Strongly Agree
Weighted Average Mean		3.41	Strongly Agree

Note. The WAM for weighted arithmetic mean and VI for verbal interpretation was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.75 indicates Strongly Disagree (SD), the range of 1.76 - 2.50 indicates Disagree (D), the range of 2.51 - 3.25 indicates Agree (A), and 3.26 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree (SA).

DISCUSSION

Part I. Game-Based Assessment Tools

Game-Based Assessment Tools Utilized in Physical Education Classes in terms of Written Works

Table 1 presents the game-based assessment tools utilized for written works in PE classes. The Sport Skill Relay Strategy emerged as the highest frequently used tool, accounting for Frequency of (28) and Percentage of (25%) responses, while the lowest Frequency of (1) and Percentage of (.9%) are the Catch and Throw Games, Fitness Bingo Strategy, Capture the Flag Strategy, Simon Says Strategy, Fitness Tic-Tac-Toe Strategy.

The data explicitly shows that PE teachers integrate physically engaging strategies into traditionally non-physical assessments like written works. This highlights their intention to merge kinesthetic learning with conceptual understanding. The preference for these tools suggests that even theoretical components of PE are being gamified to maintain interest and reinforce knowledge retention through active participation.

Prieto and Aguilar (2022) emphasized that strategies like Catch and Throw facilitate both social and cognitive development by involving learners in dynamic activities.

The researchers agree that incorporating these types of interactive methods not only assesses student understanding more effectively but also fosters a more engaging and meaningful learning environment. By observing how written works are gamified, the researchers believe that students are more likely to retain theoretical knowledge when it is embedded in fun and competitive contexts.

Game-Based Assessment Tools Utilized in Physical Education Classes in terms of Performance Task

Table 2 presents the distribution of game-based tools used in PE performance tasks. The Relay Race Challenge emerged as the highest frequently used tool, accounting for Frequency of (30) and Percentage of (26.8%) responses, while the lowest Frequency of 1 and Percentage of .9% are the Throwing Accuracy Challenge, Catching and Dodging, Fitness Circuit, Target Shooting Challenge, and Cooperative Ball Pass.

The data explicitly shows a strong inclination toward team-based, skill-oriented activities in performance assessment. These tasks not only require motor proficiency but also foster collaborative and strategic thinking. The use of varied physical challenges ensures a comprehensive evaluation of students' physical competence and cooperative abilities.

Martin-Kniep (2022) noted that performance assessments in PE should simulate real-world tasks that integrate knowledge, skills, and attitudes. The researchers support this view, believing that the application of GBA in actual skill tasks like relay races and team games mirrors real-life physical experiences and social situations. This allows for deeper learning beyond memorization, promoting teamwork, coordination, and decision-making among students

Part II. Perceived Effects of the Utilization of Game-based Assessment Tools

Perceived Effects of the Utilization of Game-Based Assessment Tools in terms of Engagement

The result of this study can be linked to the study of Jabbar and Felicia (2015), who asserted that game-based strategies lead to higher cognitive and emotional engagement. Similarly, Mitchell and Co (2024) highlighted that gamified instruction improves classroom interaction and focus. The researchers agree that increased student engagement stems from the novelty and excitement of games, which make routine assessments feel less intimidating and more rewarding. As a result, students are more willing to participate actively, contributing to a livelier, more collaborative PE class environment.

Perceived Effects of the Utilization of Game-Based Assessment Tools in terms of Motivation

Table 4 presents students perceived motivational responses to GBA. Statement number nine (9) got the highest WAM (3.57), “Enhances my confidence with my abilities”, while statement number seven (7) got the lowest WAM (3.42) “Makes me want to practice my skills outside of class”. The overall WAM average of (3.48) Strongly Agree.

Students reported that GBA tools significantly increased their motivation in Physical Education. The highest-rated statement showed improved self-confidence, suggesting that these activities help students believe more in their abilities. Several items also reflected increased excitement to learn and a desire to improve performance. This indicates that game-based strategies create a motivational learning environment that supports both individual growth and teamwork.

Lin (2024) and Duterte (2024) emphasized that game-based learning environments enhance motivation through elements of achievement, control, and challenge. The researchers interpret these findings to mean that students experience a sense of ownership and accomplishment during GBA activities, which fuels their internal drive. Through structured competition and cooperative goals, learners become more invested in the outcomes, which reinforces their motivation to learn and perform.

Perceived Effects of the Utilization of Game-Based Assessment Tools in terms of Learners Achievements

Table 5 on the next page presents the impact of GBA on student learning achievement. Statement number eight (8) got the highest WAM (3.46), “Gives me the chance to show what I know and what I can do in PE”, while statement number five (5) got the lowest WAM (3.30), “Help me track my progress”. The overall WAM average of (3.41) Strongly Agree.

Results showed that students believe GBA enhances their learning achievements by allowing them to demonstrate and apply what they know. The highest-rated response highlighted opportunities to show skills and knowledge, reinforcing the value of practical application. Though the lowest-rated item focused on progress tracking, it still showed strong agreement, reflecting a positive view overall. These findings suggest that GBA promotes better understanding, skill development, and performance in PE.

Hassan and Yusof (2019) reported that gamified assessments enhanced learning performance by integrating learning with fun and goal-oriented activities. Burmich et al. (2023) also concluded that GBA fosters the practical application of learned skills. The researchers support these conclusions and believe that learners in this study benefited from GBA because it allowed them to demonstrate mastery in meaningful contexts. Tracking progress and performing in real-life simulations enabled students to see their development, promoting a deeper and more functional type of learning.

Part III. Output of the Study

The “Teacher’s Implementation Guide for Game-Based Assessment in Physical Education” presents a comprehensive framework for incorporating interactive and engaging assessment methods into Senior High School PE classes. It emphasizes the use of Game-Based Assessment (GBA), which blends gameplay with formal evaluation, enabling students to demonstrate their psychomotor skills, strategic thinking, and teamwork in a fun, dynamic way. The guide aims to increase motivation and participation by using top GBA tools such as the Sport Skill Relay Strategy, Catch and Throw Games, and Fitness Tic-Tac-Toe, which are designed to reinforce learning while fostering enjoyment and active involvement.

The guide outlines specific objectives students should achieve, including demonstrating practical knowledge through games, applying physical and mental skills in structured tasks, and reflecting on their performance. Assessment components are divided into written works (25%) and performance tasks (50%), with detailed sample activities provided. Each game includes clear objectives, materials, step-by-step procedures, and evaluation methods. Reflection prompts are integrated to promote student self-awareness and deeper learning, encouraging them to assess how strategy, skill execution, and teamwork contributed to their outcomes.

Implementation is designed for face-to-face delivery, following a structured flow: preparation, activity briefing, game execution, and reflection. It includes rubrics to assess criteria such as skill execution, effort, team interaction, and rule adherence. The guide also emphasizes safety and classroom management, recommending hydration breaks, the use of safety officers, and proper equipment setup. Overall, this resource supports PE teachers in delivering effective, student-centered assessments that make learning both meaningful and enjoyable.

Conclusions

After analyzing the data, the researchers arrived at the following conclusions:

1. The Sport Skill Relay Strategy was the most used game-based assessment tool for written works. This indicates that even traditionally cognitive assessments are now being gamified to promote active learning and engagement.
2. Most respondents identified engagement as the most influential factor in the effectiveness of using game-based assessment tools in PE classes.
3. A teacher’s implementation guide entitled “Teacher’s Implementation Guide for Game-Based Assessment in Physical Education” can be used to support PE teachers in effectively implementing GBA to enhance student learning, participation, and assessment outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

1. For Grade 12 Students, students are encouraged to embrace and actively participate in game-based assessments as these strategies were shown to increase their engagement, motivation, and academic achievement.
2. For Physical Education (PE) Teachers, teachers are encouraged to utilize the Teacher's Implementation Guide developed from this research to integrate game-based assessments into their instruction.
3. For School Administrators, schools may support the integration of GBA by providing teachers with appropriate resources, facilities, and professional development.
4. For Curriculum Planners and Educational Authorities, since the study was limited to a private junior high school (Grade 12), it is recommended that curriculum developers explore the expansion of GBA strategies across multiple year levels and school types.
5. For Future Researchers, may address the limitations of this study, particularly its focus on a single grade level (Grade 12) and school type (Senior High School).

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers adhered to the highest ethical standards in the conduct of this study. Prior to data collection, informed consent was obtained from all respondents, and they were clearly informed of the purpose of the study, their voluntary participation, and their right to withdraw at any stage without any form of penalty or disadvantage. The anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were strictly maintained, and all data gathered were handled in accordance with the Data Privacy Act to ensure the protection of personal information. The physical, psychological, and emotional well-being of the respondents were safeguarded throughout the research process. The researchers declare that no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided by properly citing all sources used, and objectivity was upheld to ensure that there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings. The results of the study were used solely for academic and research purposes.

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